

The Good Samaritan as a Model for Mission Theology

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Article History:

Received: 28 June 2023

Revised: 27 July 2024

Accepted: 6 August 2024

Published: 6 August 2024

Keywords: migrant Church;
mission work; solidarity

Abstract: Focus of this article is to see the spirit of the Good Samaritan in Luke 10:25-37 as a spirit of the Church. The methodology for writing this article uses qualitative research methods with data collection techniques, data observation and interviews. This observation and interview data is complemented by a documentary study of sources from articles, books, and electronic news media. Based on the data and findings, some conclusions are drawn. This spirit of mercy in the Gospel of Luke is a manifestation towards eternal life. The mission and identity of every Christian is to embody the face of mercy in walking with the Church. The Church's discovery of the living God is truly manifested in a journey hidden in synodality. The Diocese of Tanjung Selor as part of the Asian Church has a uniqueness in that it has a mission and theology there which can be realized through the Year of Mission Solidarity. The Year of Mission Solidarity is a concrete manifestation in dealing with the situation of the local Church. In this context, the Year of Mission Solidarity is a concrete step in realizing the face of a merciful Church as Jesus commanded through the story of the Good Samaritan.

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of migration has become a central issue in contemporary theological reflection amidst the waves of globalization and the ongoing increase in mobility (Sinaga, 2023). Globalization, with all its complexities, has transformed the social, economic, and cultural landscapes worldwide, causing significant shifts in human migration patterns. This is not just about the physical movement from one place to another, but also about how identity, community, and religion adapt to these rapid changes. In this context, the emergence of the concept of the "migrant Church" becomes highly relevant and significant.

The term "migration" denotes the movement of individuals from one location to another, driven by economic, social, political, or natural factors (Boaheng et al., 2024). Those who move to foreign lands are known as migrants. Migration has been a constant feature of human history, and some Christian scholars believe it is either divinely directed, with God guiding his followers to new lands for missions, or it is a consequence of circumstances like wars and persecution forcing displacement. In the Hebrew Bible, migration is often depicted as resulting from natural disasters or divine punishment. Examples include Adam and Eve being expelled from the Garden of Eden (Gen 3:23f), Cain becoming a fugitive after murdering his brother (Gen 4:12), humanity being scattered due to their actions against God's will (Gen 11:8ff), and the Israelites being exiled to Assyria due to persistent sin (2 Kings 17:22-23). Migrations like those of Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob to Egypt, and Abimelech and his family to

Moab, were caused by famine. These migrations had both negative and positive impacts, such as loss of nationality but also gaining wealth in foreign lands.

Migration is also present in the New Testament. Jesus, as an itinerant preacher, did not stay in one place (cf. Luke 9:58). Some of his disciples left their families, homes, and careers to follow him. Migration is seen as a positive phenomenon in the New Testament, aiding in the spread of Christianity and the mission of sharing the gospel across different cultures in the ancient Graeco-Roman world. The Christian church's mission, as stated in the Great Commission (Matt. 28:19-20 and its parallels), is to make disciples of all nations. The church's global mission was empowered by the Holy Spirit on the day of Pentecost (Acts 2:1-6). The Acts of the Apostles recounts how persecution drove disciples out of Jerusalem, making them refugees and missionaries. Jerusalem and Judea, where Christianity originated, had diverse races and cultures, making migration a key strategy for spreading the faith. In the early church, missionary activities were closely linked to migration, whether voluntary or forced. The book of Acts describes people moving to new places under the influence of the Holy Spirit for the Gospel's sake. Without migration, Christianity would have remained confined to Jerusalem, with little impact on the rest of the world.

The migrant Church refers to a concept that views the church not only as an entity tied to a specific geographical location but as a community of faith that moves and adapts to the dynamics of Christian life spread across different parts of the world (Kunnath, 2023). In this sense, the church is not just a gathering place for people living in one location but also a global community capable of bridging cultural, linguistic, and background differences.

The phenomenon of migration, involving the movement of individuals or groups from one place to another, has a profound impact on social and religious structures. Migration occurs not only for economic or political reasons but also as part of a spiritual and existential search. The migrant Church seeks to address these challenges in new ways, viewing migration not as a problem to be solved but as an opportunity to understand and live out the church's mission in a broader and more diverse context.

An important aspect of the migrant Church is its ability to understand and integrate the experience of compassion in the context of migration. This involves attention to the needs and challenges faced by migrants, as well as efforts to build supportive relationships between migrants and local communities. The migrant Church emphasizes that the life and meaning of the faith community are not only derived through rituals and liturgies held within church buildings but also through compassionate and understanding interactions outside the church walls.

As a moving faith community, the migrant Church invites us to reconsider the meaning of fellowship and the church's mission in an increasingly connected and complex world. It is not only about responding to the needs of migrants with acts of love but also about how the church itself transforms and adapts to the experiences faced by its members.

This article highlights the efforts of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor in conducting an activity called the "Extraordinary Mission Year" since 2019 (Olla, 2022). This activity was

inspired by and is a follow-up to what Pope Francis conveyed on Mission Sunday, October 22, 2017. At that time, Pope Francis declared October 2019 as the Extraordinary Mission Month. The difference is that Pope Francis designated one month as the Mission Month, while the Diocese of Tanjung Selor allocated a full year for this Mission Year, rotating between parishes up to the present. The Extraordinary Mission Year in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor practically designates specific parishes as the venues for what is called the Year of Mission Solidarity. This activity is based on identifying the challenges and opportunities arising from the migration phenomenon that reflects the congregation of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor. We will see how the migrant Church can become a relevant model for faith communities in the future, considering the needs and realities of migrants and their relationships with local communities (Bevans, 2002). In this way, it is hoped that contemporary theological reflection on migration will provide deeper insights into how the church can remain relevant and effective in this ever-changing world.

In the contemporary the Diocese of Tanjung Selor context where migration is a common phenomenon, the church can learn from the missional consequences of the migration of the early Christians. Thus, there are two new aspects in this research. First, the focus of this research is directed towards the discourse on the renewal of the Tanjung Selor Church concerning Luke 10:25-37. Second, the pastoral implications related to mission theology in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor.

METHOD

The methodology used in this research is a qualitative approach that results in a description of speculative theology. This qualitative research attempts to understand the Good Samaritan as a model of theology. The type of research is qualitative-descriptive, with data collection methods focusing on literature review. Relevant data are collected from various written sources, including books, scholarly journals, and newspapers, as supporting materials. In this context, the subject being studied is the spirit of the Samaritan in Luke 10:25-37. The creation of a model aims to deepen information, reconstruct, and ultimately draw descriptive conclusions supported by documentation. Data analysis is then conducted with verification and conclusion drawing, which shows the correlation between the spirit of the Samaritan and the Year of Mission Solidarity of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor, Indonesia.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The local church of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor was established based on a decree from Pope John Paul II dated December 22, 2001 (Harjosusanto & Wiyanto, 2011). The establishment of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor based on Pope John Paul II's decree was only announced later on January 9, 2002. On April 14, 2002, Father Yustinus Harjosusanto was consecrated as the first bishop of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor. Previously, the area of the Tanjung Selor Church was part of the pastoral area of the Archdiocese of Samarinda, which was the only diocese in the province of East Kalimantan, Indonesia (Tedy et al., 2022; Gegel, 2022). The extensive pastoral area necessitated the formation of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor in the northern region of East Kalimantan. In terms of time, the Diocese of Tanjung Selor is

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relatively "new" compared to other dioceses in Indonesia.

At its inception, the Diocese of Tanjung Selor consisted of only 10 parishes spread across 2 regencies (currently, there are 15 parishes spread across 2 provinces, 5 regencies, and 1 municipality). The pastoral area of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor covers the entire province of North Kalimantan (a province formed a decade later) and part of the East Kalimantan province. The total area of this pastoral region is 96,630 km² (Harjosusanto & Wiyanto, 2011). This area is quite large compared to the relatively small and scattered congregation.

Based on the geographical map, the Tanjung Selor Church covers a vast area. Meanwhile, based on the statistical number of congregants, the Tanjung Selor Church is considered small. The number of Catholics is even smaller compared to the Protestant Christian population. This can be understood as the Tanjung Selor area received Protestant missions earlier than Catholic ones (Pauline et al., 2021).

The implementation of the Year of Mission Solidarity in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor has its hopes and challenges. At least three challenges were mentioned by the Bishop of Tanjung Selor. First, the Year of Mission Solidarity, filled with various activities, emphasizes the importance of well-organized programs to ensure clear direction. Second, it is important for the congregation to have a proper understanding of missionary theology and spirituality. Third, the organization of the Year of Mission Solidarity requires financial support.

From the outset, the inception of the Year of Mission Solidarity in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor was also in the spirit of synodality as echoed by Pope Francis. There is an indication that the parish churches in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor, each with its unique situation, have lacked attention to their existence as the people of God walking together in the diocese. From this, the Bishop of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor initiated the Year of Mission Solidarity to ensure that each parish in the diocese becomes truly aware of its responsibility to show solidarity with other parishes within the same diocese.

The Diocese of Tanjung Selor is characterized by a context of diversity. This diversity is not only in terms of local social and cultural aspects but also includes religion, educational background, and occupation. The existence and presence of the Church in this place contribute to the diversity of the community's life while also having an influence, at least in terms of public policy.

The diversity in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor is closely influenced by its geographical location. Although the island of Kalimantan is generally associated with the Dayak population and culture, Tanjung Selor is somewhat different. Its location at the northern tip of Kalimantan makes it a strategic place and route. This is because Tanjung Selor directly borders Malaysia and the Sulawesi Sea. It is unavoidable that the demographics of Tanjung Selor are influenced by communities from Sulawesi and various other places (Java, Flores, and other groups), and it serves as an entry and exit route for international movement. All of this potentially builds a peaceful coexistence in diversity but also poses a risk for conflict due to its heterogeneity.

From a social perspective, Tanjung Selor is diverse in terms of ethnicity, religion, educational background, and occupation (Christover, 2019). So far, religious identity conflicts

have not been prominent. Conflicts generally arise from ethnic identity issues. Meanwhile, the indigenous people generally have a lower level of education. Those with higher education degrees are usually from the transmigrant communities who mostly live in urban areas. This educational background determines the occupations of the people in Tanjung Selor. Although the general populace works as rice farmers, the entry of external companies (palm oil, coal, timber, and others) opens up opportunities for the community to work as laborers (Harjosusanto & Wiyanto, 2011). Those with diplomas generally work as civil servants or contract workers and company employees, while those without education work as farmers and laborers in the companies.

The Tanjung Selor Church is identified as a Migrant Church (Siagian, 2021). Sinaga (2023) is well aware of this migrant identity in his theological thinking. The migrant Church refers to a church that functions and develops among migrant groups. In many cases, this church serves as a bridge connecting Christians who are separated from their original communities with their new surroundings. The migrant Church not only acts as a place of worship but also as a center of social, emotional, and spiritual support for those in transition and often in vulnerable situations. Through the lens of theology, the migrant Church is a manifestation of Christ's love that transcends cultural, national, and linguistic boundaries, offering comfort and hope to those struggling in the migration process. As migrants, the Church is aware that its existence depends on the compassion of others. This is the spirit of mission in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor, a spirit of embracing one another on the journey together towards its fullness as a Church.

In a social context, the migrant Church acts as an agent of change and advocate for justice. The migrant Church often finds itself at the forefront of addressing challenges faced by migrants, such as legal difficulties, discrimination, and economic uncertainty. Through acts of compassion, the migrant Church strives to create a safe and inclusive space where migrants can feel accepted and valued. This Church provides practical support, such as legal services and social assistance, as well as spiritual support through programs that promote the emotional and psychological well-being of migrants.

The Church, as a divine and human reality, should not only be preoccupied with its human aspects. The call to care for and show compassion (solidarity) is also an eschatological call. The Year of Mission Solidarity is an important moment to fulfill the Church's mission.

The expected fruits of the mission of solidarity in the Diocese of Tanjung Selor simply mean that each parish should care for one another. This is important because the Church is the people of God journeying together towards its fullness. Difficult times experienced by one parish in the diocese should concern all the parishes in the diocese. It is not enough for a parish to be satisfied with itself and its achievements.

This writing aims to build a spirit of mission, drawing inspiration from the spirit of the Good Samaritan in Luke 10:25-37. This parable, unique to the evangelist Luke, is delivered by Jesus in response to a question about how to inherit eternal life. The context of the parable is about who becomes a neighbor in difficult times. Jesus' answer emphasizes that a neighbor is

not determined by identity (whether Pharisee, Sadducee, or Samaritan) but by the good deeds performed.

Compassion is at the heart of the theology of the migrant Church. This concept of compassion not only focuses on helping those in need but also on a deep understanding of solidarity and empathy built within the relationship between the Church and migrants. In the context of the Gospel, compassion is one of the main attributes of Christian identity. Jesus Christ, as the ultimate example, showed His compassion through concrete actions in serving and caring for the marginalized. In Luke 10:25-37, the parable of the Good Samaritan teaches that compassion is not limited by ethnic or social boundaries but extends to all who need help, regardless of their background.

This story serves as a model for the Church in living out compassion, where compassion is a Christian identity (Suardana, 2015). The Samaritan in Luke 10 is a simple command for every Christian to help one another. Helping is the simplest form and way of theology. Even though Jews did not associate with Samaritans, Jesus highlighted the Samaritan as the Compassionate One to emphasize that the value of helping leads one to eternal life. The context of eternal life in this parable has an eschatological nuance, indicating that every Christian is called to embark on the journey toward eternal life with solidarity and mutual assistance. This is the mission of every Christian pilgrim in the world.

The parable of the Good Samaritan in Luke 10:25-37 serves as a model for the Church in living out compassion. Compassion becomes the face and identity of Christians (Suardana, 2015). The Samaritan in Luke 10 is a simple command for every Christian to help one another. Helping is the simplest form and way of theology. Although Jews did not associate with Samaritans, Jesus highlighted the Samaritan as the Compassionate One to emphasize that the value of helping leads one to eternal life. The context of eternal life in this parable has an eschatological nuance, indicating that every Christian is called to embark on the journey toward eternal life with solidarity and mutual assistance. This is the mission of every Christian pilgrim in the world.

This text aims to show the Church that salvation was first promised to the people of Israel. The reflection on eternal salvation culminates in Jesus Christ, who offers salvation as a universal path for all people. The Gospel of John clearly presents this aspect. The Holy Scriptures are a narrative of God's love for humanity, and the Bible is a book of faith. Reading the Scriptures becomes more useful and transformative when done in faith in Christ. The salvation initially offered to the people of Israel does not preclude its availability to other nations, as represented by the Samaritans.

Theology of connectivity (Firmanto et al., 2023) is one of the important aspects of the theology of the migrant Church. The migrant Church does not operate in isolation but interacts and integrates with the local community. This connectivity reflects Christ's teachings on living in community and building supportive relationships. In this relationship, the migrant Church plays a dual role as both a servant and a recipient of service, meaning that both the migrant Church and the local community can learn and grow through this interaction. This creates

opportunities for dialogue and better understanding between different cultures and backgrounds, and strengthens social and spiritual bonds within the broader community. Therefore, every Christian is called to realize the journey towards eternal life with a spirit of solidarity and mutual assistance, as exemplified by the Good Samaritan. This is the mission of every Christian pilgrim in the world, reflecting compassion as their identity and manifesting the face of Christ through concrete actions in daily life.

The migrant experience often involves significant struggles and challenges. In facing uncertainty and difficulties, compassion becomes a source of strength and comfort. The migrant Church, with its compassionate and empathetic approach, serves as a place where migrants can find the practical and spiritual support they need. Through acts of compassion, the migrant Church helps migrants navigate the various challenges they face and provides them with hope for the future. This experience reinforces the belief that compassion is not just an act but also an attitude and way of life that shapes how the Church operates and interacts with the world around it.

Compassion in the context of the migrant Church also has the potential to influence broader social change. By focusing on the needs and challenges faced by migrants, the migrant Church can become an agent of change that promotes fairer and more inclusive policies and practices. The migrant Church can collaborate with other institutions to advocate for migrants' rights and encourage policies that support their well-being. Additionally, through consistent and coordinated acts of compassion, the migrant Church can help build a more just society that cares for the needs of others, thereby creating positive and sustainable social change. Gultom (2022) states that the theory of God's philanthropy serves as a foundation in the practice of giving alms to the poor and sharing as a reflection of God's originality. Christianity is identified with Jesus, who is not greedy and is kind-hearted with the goal of salvation through the restoration of human life.

Sinaga (2023) posits that Migration Theology has three main reflections: migration as a depiction of the "exodus existence" of humanity, migration as a place to encounter the Stranger (God), and migration as a challenge to the Catholicity of the Church of Christ. First, the exodus existence of humanity portrays the journey of human life as a continuous migration, reflecting the biblical narrative of the exodus of the Israelites from slavery in Egypt to the promised land. In this context, migration becomes a powerful metaphor for understanding the spiritual and physical journey of humans in seeking a better and more meaningful place. This exodus existence emphasizes that human life is a pilgrimage, where humans are always on a journey towards fulfillment and self-realization, both in worldly and spiritual life.

Second, migration as a place to encounter the "Stranger" signifies that in the migration journey, humans not only move physically from one place to another but also experience encounters with God, often depicted as the Stranger. God, present amidst the migration experience, reminds us of the divine presence that always accompanies human journeys. Migration becomes a sacred moment where humans can find God in unexpected situations, in vulnerability, and openness to others. God who migrates in the person of Jesus Christ is a

concrete example of God's presence among humanity, bringing a message of reconciliation and love that transcends cultural, racial, and national boundaries.

Third, migration as a challenge to the Catholicity of the Church of Christ emphasizes that the Church must be able to respond to the reality of migration with an inclusive and accepting attitude. Migration challenges the Church to broaden its understanding and ministry, reaching out to those on the peripheries and often regarded as strangers. The Second Vatican Council states that the Church is "a pilgrim in a foreign land," indicating that the Church's identity is itself as a community always on a journey, always open to others, and always seeking ways to live out Christ's message in an ever-changing context. Without migration, there would be no Christianity and no Church in the world, as the core of Christ's message is to cross boundaries and bring the good news to all people without exception.

Thus, biologically and spiritually, humans have migration within them, and this is a sign of the Church and Christianity. Migration is not only a physical phenomenon but also a profound spiritual reality, reflecting the condition of humans as beings always on a journey, always seeking meaning and place in this world. Sinaga (2023) offers Migration Theology by articulating an understanding of the relationship between God and humans through an eschatological approach. God who migrates in Jesus Christ and is present among humans becomes the basis for understanding Christ's mission in responding to the reality of migration. Jesus Christ, in his migration, shows the way for humanity to reconcile the broken relationships between God and humans, as well as among humans themselves. In the context of migration, the Church is called to be an inclusive community that welcomes and supports migrants. The Church should see migration as an opportunity to manifest Christ's love in concrete ways, through actions that help migrants overcome the challenges they face. Migration becomes a platform to fulfill the Church's calling as an agent of reconciliation and peacemaker, connecting humans with God and with one another in a spirit of love and solidarity.

The eschatological approach in Migration Theology emphasizes that the migration journey is part of humanity's pilgrimage toward ultimate fulfillment before God (Aprianto & Astuti, 2023). Migration, with all its difficulties and challenges, is part of the process of spiritual formation and growth that brings people closer to God. God, who is present in the migration of Jesus Christ, shows that in every step of human journeys, God is always accompanying and guiding towards the ultimate goal, which is perfect communion with Him. Moreover, Migration Theology also calls on the church to be more sensitive to the socio-political realities affecting migrants' lives. The church must boldly speak out and act against injustice, discrimination, and exploitation that migrants often face. In the spirit of Christ, the church is called to be a voice for the voiceless, providing protection and support for those marginalized and oppressed. The church should be a safe haven where everyone is accepted and valued as God's precious creation. Migration as a challenge to the Catholicity of the Church of Christ also means that the church must continually renew itself, always seeking new ways to serve and reach out to those in migration situations. The church must not be rigidly bound by structure and tradition but be flexible and adaptive, ready to respond to the needs of the

times. Inclusivity and openness are key for the church to remain relevant and meaningful in an ever-changing world.

Sinaga (2023) reminds us that the church's mission is to bring the good news to everyone, especially those most in need. The church must dare to step out of its comfort zone and actively engage in the life of the community, bringing a message of love and hope to those on the migration journey. Thus, the church becomes a living witness to God's universal love, crossing all boundaries and bringing peace to all creation.

Sinaga (2023) also emphasizes the importance of solidarity and empathy in facing the reality of migration. The church must develop a deep sense of empathy for migrants, understand their struggles and suffering, and strive to provide tangible support. This solidarity is not just material assistance but also emotional and spiritual support that helps migrants feel accepted and valued.

In the context of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor, where migration is a significant phenomenon, the church plays an important role in supporting and advocating for migrants' rights. The church should collaborate with the government, non-governmental organizations, and local communities to create a conducive environment for migrants, where they can live with dignity and security (Saleh et al., 2023). The church should also be involved in educating and raising community awareness about the importance of accepting and respecting migrants as part of the broader community.

The Migration Theology offered by Sinaga (2023) provides a strong theological framework for understanding and responding to the reality of migration in the modern world. By placing migration in an eschatological context and understanding the relationship between God and humans, the church can find deeper meaning in its ministry to migrants. The church is called to be an agent of reconciliation, a bearer of peace, and a witness to God's love that transcends all boundaries. In the spirit of Christ, the church must embrace migrants with love and solidarity, bringing hope and comfort in their journey toward their ultimate goal before God (Sugiyana et al., 2024; Surip et al., 2024; Tefa, 2023).

In the context of the above theology of the migrant Church, the Church of Tanjung Selor is essentially a Church also called to attain salvation through compassion. It would be quite strange if, within the diocese's context, parish churches do not share a vision of realizing salvation for all people through compassionate actions. In this sense, the significance of the mission solidarity year truly finds its place when situated in the actual pastoral practice context of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor today. Many people genuinely hope for compassion from others to be involved in their lives, struggles, and efforts toward unity in the path of salvation. Unity is a crucial keyword, considering that the Church of Tanjung Selor is a church of migrants. In theological reflection, the migrant Church finds meaning and purpose in its compassionate service (Nayoan, 2021). The theology of the migrant Church emphasizes the importance of following Christ's example in serving those in need, regardless of their background or circumstances. This reflects a broader understanding of the Christian calling to be agents of compassion and positive change in the world (Edison et al., 2023; Susilo et al.,

2023). Practically, this means that the migrant Church must continuously evaluate and adjust its approach to ensure that it meets the community's needs in the most effective and relevant way.

CONCLUSION

Theology and mission in Asia have unique challenges due to the richness of Asia itself. Each place even has its own specific and unique context. The Tanjung Selor Church, as part of the Asian Church, also has a unique situation. Mission means paying attention to the context in which the Church is located. As a distinctive Church with various issues and richness, the Year of Mission Solidarity initiated by the Tanjung Selor Church for its community is taken seriously. This is the model of theology intended by the Second Vatican Council, where the Church grows from the grassroots, developing itself towards the fullness of Christian life. Reflecting on the story of the Good Samaritan in Luke 10:25-37, the identity of the Tanjung Selor Church is a compassionate Church. Compassion is first manifested within itself so that it truly becomes a living proclamation of the truth. The story of the Samaritan's generosity serves as a mission theology model for the Tanjung Selor diocesan Church.

The theology of the migrant Church that gains life through compassion illustrates how the Church can function as an agent of change and support amidst the challenges of migration. By focusing on compassion as the foundation of mission and service, the migrant Church not only assists individuals experiencing migration but also enriches the community as a whole by providing a tangible example of Christ's love. Through compassionate interactions and practical support, the migrant Church plays a vital role in building inclusive and just communities and promoting positive social change. In fulfilling this calling, the migrant Church demonstrates that compassion is key to a better and more sustainable life for everyone, both within the migrant community and the local society.

Acknowledgement: The authors acknowledge parishioners of the Diocese of Tanjung Selor who helped the authors collect data, analyze, and write this research article.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared that the research results that have been carried out are free from conflicts of interest from certain parties who may claim the results of their research.

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